

Daily Administration and Network Management Plan

Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme
H2020-MSCA-ITN-2014
Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions

Project no.: 642877
Project acronym: InnoChain
Project title: Building Innovation in the Extended Digital Chain

Start date of the project: 01/09/2015
Duration of the project: 48 months

Workpackage: 1 - Management
Task: 1.2

Organisation name of lead beneficiary for this task: CITA
Authors: Martin Tamke (CITA)

Dissemination Level: Other

R Document, report
DEM Demonstrator, pilot, prototype
DEC Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.
OTHER

Table of Content

1 Introduction

2 Daily management of the network

2.1 Daily management key tasks

2.2 Role of the Network Administrator

2.3 Monthly management meetings

3 Network internal collaboration and communication infrastructure

3.1 Electronic Mailing Lists

3.2 Video conferencing

3.3 Internal Web platform

4 Management of Deliverables to the EU

4.1 Timing of Deliverables:

Appendix 1: Milestones in the project

Appendix 2 : Deliverables to the EC

1 Introduction

This document provides information on the daily management of Innochain and supplements the general management structure described in the document “Management Structure”. It describes the procedures and tasks for the handling of the project by the Supervisor Board and the Network Administrator (NA), the way how the network exchanges and administers internally and how it collaborates on the deliverables to the European Commission.

The document provides further more an overview over the milestones and deliverables, which guide the management of the network.

2 Daily management of the network

The Network Administrator is central figure in the daily administration of the network and collaborates with the members of the supervisory board in this duty. The Network Administrator is sited at CITA to support his/her coordination of the network

2.1 Daily management key tasks

The key tasks include:

- 1) Maintain a central port of call for:
 - beneficiary, industry partner and ESR questions on project status and planning
 - beneficiary, industry partner and ESRs for questions about evaluation, training and dissemination
 - communication with EU-Officer
- 2) Establish a central information hub for the network that:
 - collects information from beneficiaries, industry partners and ESRs on Innochain related activities (industry collaborations, secondments, evaluation, training, dissemination events)
 - distributes and maintains general network information (calendar of evaluation, training and evaluation events)
 - create and maintain a repository of scientific publications and datasets made within Innochain
- 3) Support network activities including:

- Work package management, assembly and creation of deliverables, network journals and the extended catalogue
 - beneficiary organisation of teaching activities
 - everyday handling, monitoring and creation of external communication (webpage, facebook and other web platforms)
- 4) Management and delivery of all project reports (project related and financial) to the EC

2.2 Role of the Network Administrator

The network administrator will handle the everyday administration of the network. Further key tasks are:

- log secondments and collaboration with industry partners
- prepare management meetings
- administrate and support meetings, including invitations, agendas, capturing meeting minutes, support and generate post-meeting communication and follow-up on decisions.
- maintain contact- and mailinglists of Innochain
- manage the Innochain calendar

In the setup phase the network administrator will furthermore help to:

- setup internal communication platform
- setup external communication platform
- setup of formats for deliverables

The Network administrator does not handle the economy of the individual partners and their ESRs.

2.3 Monthly management meetings

A central means of steering the network is the monthly Supervision Board management meeting. The Supervision Board will here monitor and coordinate the daily administration including the organisation of evaluation, training and dissemination events.

Recurring topics of the monthly meetings include:

- status of ESR progress and industry collaboration
- report from Work Package Committees
- planning and evaluation of training and dissemination events
- information about intended dissemination activities
- mutual update of opportunities for dissemination, collaboration and synergies within and for the network

The monthly meetings are minuted by the Network Administrator and shared on the internal communication platform.

3 Network internal collaboration and communication infrastructure

The large part of the collaboration and communication within Innochain will take place across digital media. The following sections outline the infrastructure of the use of digital media platforms.

3.1 Electronic Mailing Lists

In order to ease email communication network specific mailing lists are setup using mailchimp. Mailchimp will be setup by IAAC for the following lists:

- all
- Supervisor Board
- Steering Board
- Industry board
- Work Package committees 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6
- all ESR

3.2 Video conferencing

Video conferencing will be used across the project for

- general Innochain management
- industry collaboration
- planning, running and evaluation of ESR training
- work package coordination

The following virtual conference infrastructure is used across all four use scenarios.- :

- Skype for Business for groups of 2 -4
- Google Hangout for groups of 4 - 10
- Adobe Connect for conferences with more than 10 participants

3.3 Internal Web platform

The internal web platform provides the network with a central and private entry to information and communication related to the collaboration, management and administration on three levels:

- the network in general
- the evaluation, training and dissemination programme
- the work of the work packages and individual projects

The primary function of the internal web platform is to provide a central point of entry to the many streams of communications which will naturally occur in the network. In a large and heterogeneous network as Innochain members will use easy, available and, in terms of industrial partners, often prescribed means of communication for their individual communication and handling of project related tasks.

The internal web platform serves as a repository for the decisions and the decision taking process in the management of the network.

Content of the internal web platform

- **Calendar** with teaching plan, meetings, conferences and other events of interest to the network (linked through google calendar to www.innochain.net)
- **Meetings and minutes** (for preparation and documentation of meetings and all other events in the network)
- **Administration & Templates**
 - Administrative Documents (grant agreement, management agreements, IP agreements, gender support plan, reports to EU etc.)
 - Templates for deliverables (word, latex), extended catalogues, workshop seminar journals, letters (word), posters (Indesign), logos, presentations etc.
- **Work packages** (for organisation of workshop events and central entry point to related information)
- **Deliverables** (Table of Contents, draft versions, discussions, reviews)
- **Contacts & Links** (Name, Organisation, email, Telephone, Skype)
 - Entry point to social media and 3rd party web platforms (flickr, instagram, github etc.)
- Possible extensions (as needed):
 - Internal work and discussion environments for projects
 - Central repository for bibliography, references
 - Researchers forum for internal exchange / chat

4 Management of Deliverables to the EU

A well structured and efficient process for the reporting to the EU is required in order to guarantee high quality and timely delivery. The network agreed on the following measures, which shall guarantee this:

- Unified format for deliverables following the Innochain templates published on the internal web platform
- Use of the internal web platform as central point of entry to the writing and review process of the deliverable
- Web based collaboration on the deliverables (ie. through google doc or latex on institutions svn servers)
- Internal review of deliverable by two peers

4.1 Timing of Deliverables:

Due Date minus	Action
- 2 months	publishing of deliverable TOC and definition of internal reviewers (on internal web platform)
- 1month	internal submission of Deliverables to internal reviewers (on internal web platform)
- 2 week	internal reviewers provide feedback (on internal web platform)
- 4 days	authors send final deliverable to the network administrator
- 1 day	upload of Deliverable to EU through the network administrator

5 Appendix 1: Milestones in the project

The daily administration is guided by the following nine milestones. These are described in Chapter 1.3.4. WT4 “List of milestones of the innohain” Grant agreement.

Milestone number	Milestone title	WP numbers engaged	Lead beneficiary	Due Date (in months)	Means of verification
MS1	Review of requirements (network agreements, recruitment, web platforms)	WP1	1 - CITA	6	Completion and internal publication of key required agreements for project operation including: Consortium Agreement, Daily Administration and Network Management Plan, File sharing management, Gender Support Plan and IPR Management Plan. Completion of full recruiting and trouble shooting of any late starting ESR appointments. Completion of recruitment of network administrator. Setup of web based file sharing system. Completion of web based blog portal.
MS2	Workshop-Seminar 1	WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5	3 - ITKE	12	Completion of workshop- seminar report. Evaluation of scientific progress and synergy in the three sub- tracks. Review of strategies for implementation.
MS3	First year colloquium and research exhibition “Design Probes”	WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6	4 - IOA	18	Completion of colloquium and publication of exhibition journal. Evaluation of research progress in the individual research projects and across the 3 sub-tracks. Review of shared experimental methodology. Review and evaluation of industrial collaboration and secondment programme including the first secondment period. Review of overall dissemination and publication strategy. Completion of workshop-seminar report.

					Evaluation of scientific progress and synergy in the three sub- tracks. Review of strategies for implementation.
MS4	Workshop-Seminar 2	WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6	3 - ITKE	24	Completion of workshopseminar report. Evaluation of scientific progress and synergy in the three subtracks. Review of strategies for implementation.
MS5	Second year colloquium and research exhibition "Prototypes"	WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6	6 - IAAC	30	Completion of colloquium and exhibition journal. Evaluation on research progress in the individual research projects and across the 3 sub-tracks. Review of shared experimental methodology. Review and evaluation of industrial collaboration and secondment programme including the first secondment period. Review of overall dissemination and publication strategy.
MS6	Pre-viva seminar	WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5	3 - ITKE	36	Completion of pre-viva seminar report. Evaluation on research progress in the individual research projects and the 3 sub-tracks. Review and evaluation of industrial collaboration and secondment programme including the first secondment period.
MS7	Final exam (VIVA)	WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5	1 - CITA	42	Completion of all PhD exams. Evaluation of overall research excellence and innovation.
MS8	International conference and research exhibition "Demonstrators"	WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6	1 - CITA	45	Completion of international conference and exhibition. Review of overall dissemination and publication strategy. Review with industrial partnership for further implementation and commercialisation of results.
MS9	Extended Catalogue	WP6	1 - CITA	47	Completion of final reporting of research results. Review of results and their contextualisation in industrial context.

6 Appendix 2 : Deliverables to the EC

The following Deliverables will be submitted to the European Commission during the project. This list is in accordance with the chapter 1.3.2 "WT2 list of deliverables" of the innochain Grant Agreement.

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Title	WP	Lead beneficiary	Type	Dissemination level	Due Date (in months)
D1.1	Progress Report	WP1	CITA	Report	Confidential *	13
D1.2	Mid-term review meeting	WP1	CITA	Other	Confidential *	26
D1.3	Draft Periodic Report	WP1	CITA	Report	Confidential *	24
D1.4	Supervisory Board of the network	WP1	CITA	Other	Confidential *	2
D1.5	Updated Data Management Plan	WP1	CITA	Report	Public	24
D2.1	Workshop-seminar 1	WP2	ITKE	Other	Public	14
D2.2	Workshop-seminar 2	WP2	KTH	Other	Public	26
D3.1	Research exhibition "Design Probes" and colloquia 1	WP3	IOA	Other	Public	19
D4.1	Research exhibition "Prototypes" and colloquia 2	WP4	IAAC	Other	Public	31
D5.1	Research exhibition "Demonstrators" and VIVA	WP5	CITA	Other	Public	42
D6.1	Concluding international conference and extended catalogue	WP6	BSA	Other	Public	45
D6.2	Website development	WP6	CITA	Websites, patents filling etc.	Public	6

*Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)